

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Regulatory framework and best practices of data linkage and interoperability for disease registries and health information systems in Europe: literature and legal review

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Abstract

Background

Data linkage is a methodology used to pool information from different data sources and to produce population-based indicators for policy making. Linking various data sources improves the completeness and comprehensiveness of information to guide effective patient care and improve the performance of health services.

In the field of non-communicable diseases (NCDs), data linkage is particularly needed to investigate the disease burden and progression, risk factors, care pathways and long-term outcomes for a range of related conditions. While many countries have invested to increase their capacity in data linkage and interoperability, wide differences still co-exist in Europe.

This report aims to provide an update of the current challenges and solutions, providing key recommendations for data holders on how to overcome the hurdles experienced in disease registries and health information systems for the routine production of NCD indicators.

Methods

Literature review of current regulations and relevant papers published in the scientific and grey literature. The set of recommendations were drawn from legal analysis and the appraisal of results of European projects, with particular attention for their potential impact on the implementation of the European Health Data Space (EHDS).

Results

Study findings highlighted the main obstacles associated with the implementation and use of data linkage, including a) complex laws and data protection regulations, which hinder linkage between different data sources with a deterministic approach (legal); and b) lack of governance measures in health information (data governance).

The estimation of NCD indicators from linked administrative data can be hampered by the variability in data sources and data collection methods, the availability of a large number of variables, and the lack of skills and capacity to analyse large scale databases.

Conclusions

Meeting the requirements set by data protection legislation in data processing operations is a prerequisite for the implementation of a sustainable information system enabling the routine collection of EU-harmonised indicators for diabetes and other NCDs.

Practical recommendations for data controllers include how best to fulfil the requirements in terms of the legal base for data processing, data subject rights, accountability and security. Privacy-preserving practices on data linkage should be also duly considered. Recommendations for data governance include how data controllers can ensure optimal data-processing operations, such as data quality and integrity, access control and transparency, data sharing and training and awareness.

The implementation of the EHDS Regulation will require that data controllers and data holders: a) ensure that health information is collected and recorded according to harmonised data formats and coding systems; b) ensure that databases are compatible with the Electronic Health Record (EHR) system, with which it communicates; and c) use of the European EHR Exchange Format.

The recommendations shall be applied to support the implementation of a sustainable information system, enabling the periodic collection of EU-harmonised NCD indicators.

1. Introduction

Under the lead of the Commission's Directorate-General of Health and Food Safety (DG SANTE), the Joint Research Centre (JRC) has launched in year 2022, a targeted initiative to deliver the essential elements of a common EU indicator framework for non-communicable diseases (NCDs). The initiative, entitled Collaborative Health Information European Framework (CHIEF), is a EU think-tank of new ideas and solutions to overcome the difficulties and hindrances towards the regular collection of NCD indicators experienced by EU projects of health information during the last two decades.

The scope of CHIEF is *“to provide expert input for the design and implementation of a sustainable information system that will enable the periodic collection and progressive scalability of an EU-harmonised set of indicators across NCDs, within the current and future flagship initiatives”*.

The initiative provides the forum through which experts can collaborate within and across different disease groups, to carry out activities that include remote and in-person work, teleconferences and annual meetings. The initial focus on diabetes will be later expanded to cover additional specific disease domains.

In order to provide a coherent link between experts and a common template for all major NCDs, different “design working groups” will be formed.

Each design working groups is expected to focus on three specific points: 1) “Meta-data”: to understand the type and contents of the documentation required to integrate the different data sources available; 2) “Federated data analysis”: to showcase a relevant set of analytical solutions needed by the EU to report on NCDs effectively, resolving the major methodological challenges; and 3. “Barriers and enablers towards implementation”: to understand the barriers hampering the implementation of regulations, with the direct participation of relevant stakeholders.

The recommendations delivered by the points of focus will define the foundations of a common health information system for the continuous monitoring of NCDs.

A series of deliverables has been identified with clear deadlines for the initial work on diabetes (through a specific “design working group” defined as “CHIEF-diabetes.dwg”). The aim of the deliverables is to ensure that indicators considered by CHIEF are not only evidence based and policy oriented, but are also feasible and achievable to collect through future pilot projects, directly from participants involved in the collaborative framework.

The present study supports CHIEF by identifying the regulatory framework for data linkage and interoperability of health information systems (including EHR systems), for the implementation of a sustainable information system that enables the periodic collection of EU-harmonised indicators for diabetes and other NCDs.

The present study aims to address the following objectives:

- Explore the state of implementation of data linkage across disease registries/health information systems that process health data relative to NCDs and identify best practices, including for deriving health indicators;
- Identify interoperability requirements and best practices in health databases/disease registries/health information systems, contained in EU and international recommendations and/or legislation, taking into account the evolution of EU legislation, in particular the Proposal for EHDS Regulation;
- Provide recommendations on legal compliance and best practices for data linkage and interoperability.

The study findings will help identify a suitable framework for data linkage and interoperability that favours the compliance with legal requirements as well as the implementation of best practices for the derivation of diabetes indicators.

The identified framework could be used as a model by EU countries to help align practices with EU regulations, such as the GDPR and the EHDS Regulation, and facilitate seamless data governance and data sharing, including across borders.

The present report will be used to determine the key elements (factors) for analysis to develop the data protection, interoperability and governance assessment (DIGA) tool, a comprehensive self-assessment instrument aimed at generating quality improvement in data management, as well as reliable information and knowledge for policy-making.

2. Materials and methods

A multidisciplinary expert team comprising all authors carried out a literature review of current regulations and relevant papers published in the scientific and grey literature.

The set of recommendations were drawn from legal analysis and the appraisal of results of European projects, with particular attention for their potential impact on the implementation of the European Health Data Space (EHDS).

The work was carried out through a series of online meetings held between November 2023-September 2024.

3. Results

This section will present the results of the literature review, ordered by data linkage, data protection, governance, best practices in data linkage and the EHDS regulation

3.1 Definition of data linkage

The availability of administrative data generated from different sources is increasing. The possibility to link these data sources with other databases offers unique opportunities to answer research questions, which require a large sample size or detailed data on hard-to reach populations (e.g. for rare diseases). With this methodology, information from different sources can be combined to generate evidence at population level with a high level of external validity and relevance for policy making. Over an extended period, data linkage enhances statistical power, thereby reducing recall bias, and incomplete data lost-to-follow up. This technique also enables more detailed stratified analyses of subgroups based on factors such as age or specific geographical regions, while providing rapid access to data collected in a standardised format¹.

The power of this approach had been acknowledged widely and proliferation of the use of data linkage is reflected in the establishment of data-linkage research centres across the EU as well as worldwide (Australia, North America, the Netherlands, the United Kingdom). In Europe, a recent review highlighted national disparities in the integration of data linkage into routine public health activities².

However, significant barriers still remain in unlocking the full potential of data linkage as a powerful research tool. First, linkage (or record matching) of data from different sources that relate to the same person depends on the availability of accurate identifiers. Imperfect identifiers can lead to linkage error, which manifest as false matches (where records belonging to different individuals are linked together) or missed matches (where records belonging to the same individual are not linked).

Moreover, linkage requires advanced expertise and skills in statistical analysis as it involves complex processes such as matching records from different data sources, handling discrepancies or missing data, and ensuring the accuracy and reliability of the linked datasets. Expertise in areas like

data cleaning, probabilistic matching algorithms, and data harmonisation is essential to overcome challenges such as inconsistent formats or varying data quality. Additionally, safeguarding privacy and adhering to ethical standards during the linkage process demands a high level of technical proficiency, as well as a deep understanding of data protection regulations. Without such advanced capabilities, the quality and validity of the research outcomes can be compromised. In order to improve data-linkage knowledge, skills and practices, InfAct partners produced methodological guidelines (<https://www.inf-act.eu/>).

The next sections will discuss several methods to evaluate the appropriate linkage strategies and the quality of linkage.

3.1.2. Types of data linkage and their use in disease registries and health information systems

Linkage methods can be differentiated by two main methodological categories: deterministic (rule based) methods and probabilistic methods. Deterministic linkage is applied when there are several identifiers that match perfectly between data sets. In this case, the match of a given identifier is evaluated as a discrete “all-or-nothing” outcome. Probabilistic linkage assigns a weight to each record pair, representing the likelihood that two records belong to the same individual, given the agreement or not between identifiers. The choice of approach is dictated by the need to balance the risk of missed matches (failing to link data from the same individual) with false matches (mistakenly linking data from different individuals). As quality assessment of data linkage is essential to limit biased results and false interpretation, several recommendations highlight elements or information about the linkage pathway (data provision, method of data linkage, and data analyses) to be shared and checked³.

Each data-linkage method comes with advantages and limitations, and the choice of which method or combination to use largely depends on the health data context (e.g. availability of indicators, data quality, legal constraints, data science capacities etc.) specific to each Member State. It also depends on the research question and the planned purpose and use of linked health data in general. The deterministic linkage method is the best exclusive option in case of generally available and usable personal identifiers with high coverage and quality in the population of interest. In all other cases various combinations of the methods are recommended⁴⁻⁷.

In addition to these two data-linkage methods, several other approaches are available to address more challenging data contexts and quality issues. For example, fully automated matching methods have been applied in other research fields, particularly in big data scenarios. These include probabilistic approaches (e.g. Epi-Weights and Fellegi-Sunter weights), unsupervised machine learning approaches (e.g. k-means clustering and bagged clustering), and supervised machine learning approaches (recursive partitioning trees, bagging of decision trees, bootstrap based classification trees, stochastic boosting, support vector machines, neural networks and logistic regression). However, all these alternative methods and approaches are yet to be tested and compared in quality (accuracy, precision, sensitivity and specificity), completeness (correctly classified matches), and efficiency (run-time) in order to find an optimal approach for matching⁸.

In 2020, the InfAct (Information for Action) Joint Action explored the differential use of data linkage in routine health monitoring based on the latest developments in new methods and analysis across European countries. InfAct involved 28 Member States and 40 health authorities. Its goal was to establish a more sustainable EU health information system (HIS) by enhancing the availability of comparable, reliable, and policy-relevant data on health status and health system performance. The main research objectives were:

- To describe the current use of data linkage at the individual level and AI techniques applied in routine public health activities;

- To identify the relevant health indicators (i.e. outcome and intervention indicators) estimated and health determinants of non-communicable diseases;
- • To identify what are the obstacles to linking different data sources in routine public health surveillance and research.

In 2020, when the research was conducted, a majority of European countries (n=24) that participated in the InfAct survey (29 out of 31)¹ performed data linkage in their routine public health activities⁹. These countries linked administrative data such as EHRs, mortality data, and disease-specific registries whereas six of them (Cyprus, Italy, Poland, Portugal, Spain and Slovakia) were developing this technique further to link with other types of data sources (i.e. demographic data, domestic/leisure accidents data, congenital anomalies registry). Ireland and Latvia had ongoing initiatives of data linkage. Three countries (Greece, Luxembourg and Romania) had not yet planned to integrate data linkage in their routine public health activities.

The following reasons were mentioned by some countries for not having institutionalised data linkage:

- Absence of a designated public health institution responsible for collecting and managing health-related data;
- Data linkage is not part of the health agenda;
- Lack of commitment from the ministry of health;
- Insufficient resources to establish a national health information system,
- The institutional complexity of the Ministry of Health;
- Strict laws and regulations, which hinder data linkage with different data sources.

These challenges highlight the need for a coordinated effort and structural reforms to streamline health data governance in many EU countries.

The majority of European countries surveyed in InfAct identified the following main obstacles associated with the implementation and the use of data linkage and advanced statistics:

- The complex laws and data protection regulations, which block linkage between different data sources with a deterministic approach (legal);
- Lack of human resources and capacities/skills within national institutes of public health and health information statistics (technical);
- Lack of governance of health information (data governance);
- Limited resources to support the health information infrastructure (organisation and structural).

3.1.3 Best practices in data linkage to estimate health indicators

Data linkage is performed routinely for different objectives, mainly for: health status monitoring; health policy development; health system performance assessment; and/or for scientific research (i.e. public health, epidemiology or clinical) purposes. Additionally, the most advanced countries such as Finland, Spain, Sweden and Scotland also perform data linkage to identify risk factors or to monitor compliance with national treatment guidelines for improving healthcare quality.

The most frequent data sources used for linkage are:

- • Health-related administrative data sources (primary care visits, emergency care, referral records, hospital discharge, prescribed medications, health insurance claims, diagnostics procedures, laboratory tests, biobanks);

- Non-health related administrative data (birth and mortality data, education level, income tax, GIS, occupation, housing conditions, criminal statistics, land and housing, socioeconomic, census (demographic), house of handicap persons, environmental, road and transport, air pollution, UV light exposure);
- Disease-specific registries (cancer, diabetes, cardiovascular, congenital malformation, tuberculosis, HIV/AIDS, inflammatory bowel disease, renal, reproductive health, dementia, organ transplantation, traffic accidents/trauma or injury, hospital registry of dome);
- National health surveys (health examination and interview surveys);
- Population-based epidemiological cohorts (e.g. DANCOS, IDEFICS, CONSTANCE, ELFE, Growing up in Scotland, HealthWise Wales cohort, Millennium cohort, Caerphilly cohort study);
- Clinical trials (e.g. FINGER, PRISMATIC).

Diabetes and diabetes-associated outcome indicators are among the most common health outcome indicators produced with help of data linkage, as reported in various domains: cardiovascular (14); neurodegenerative disease (6); maternal and perinatal health (6); diabetes (6); suicide/trauma/injury (7); cancer (6); and hepatic failure (1). The main objectives to estimate these indicators were for public health monitoring and research purposes and the level of estimation was mainly performed at national and sub-national levels.

Among health determinants, the most common factors are: physical environment (12); socioeconomic and environment (10); health behaviour and lifestyle (6); and biological and metabolic parameters (3). These determinants were used to measure the potential associations between these risk factors and health conditions for public health monitoring and research purposes.

Among the health intervention indicators, prevention and promotion of diabetes were among the most common six health conditions as reported in the domains: maternal and perinatal health (7); cancer (6); diabetes (4); cardiovascular (2); neurodegenerative disease (2); suicide/trauma/injury (1); and lower/upper respiratory infections (1). The main objectives to estimate these indicators were to guide the health policy process, public health monitoring, and research purposes.

The use of data linkage and artificial intelligence (AI) for estimating health indicators in public health have two main advantages. Firstly, data linkage improves completeness and comprehensiveness of information in order to guide health policy processes more optimally; Secondly, the extra data dimensions (features) and units (feature vectors) resulting from linkage can be used effectively by artificial intelligence applications to infer patterns that would otherwise be difficult to determine using traditional approaches.

The use of AI was not wide-spread across European countries but is increasing through initiatives such as the recent Digital Europe Programme. In the survey only five countries reported applying the following AI-related techniques in routine public health activities: machine learning (Denmark, Finland, Sweden, and UK-Wales); natural language processing (Finland, Sweden, and UK-Wales); Markov decision process (Finland); support vector machine (Finland, UK-Wales); data mining (Finland); and travelling-salesman-problem (TSP) modelling (Norway). Denmark can apply these techniques not only at a national level but also at a metropolitan level.

3.2 Privacy and data protection requirements for data processing in disease registries and health information systems

The following paragraphs examine the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) requirements¹⁰ for data processing in disease registries and health information systems, which are disease neutral by default.

Any personal data-processing occurring in disease registries or digital HIS, including data linkage, falls under the binding rules of the GDPR, which establishes the requirements that data controllers and processors have to implement when processing personal and sensitive data.

Secondary use of health data (i.e. the further processing of health data initially collected for another purpose) can provide important benefits for citizens and society and feeds directly into improving health policies. Since data linkage operations can be categorised as secondary use of data, they must comply with the GDPR requirements to ensure they respect the legal framework.

Figure 1 illustrates the privacy/data protection requirements included in the GDPR, which give an overview of the disease registry/HIS data controllers’ obligations when processing personal and sensitive data.

3.2.1 Legal base for data processing

The first requirement for processing data in disease registries/HIS is the existence of a valid legal base. The GDPR defines the legitimate legal bases according to the type of data involved, the purposes of processing and the interests at stake.

Health/health-related data falls under the category of “special categories of data” or “sensitive” data, to which special protection is accorded by Art. 9 of the GDPR.

All processing of personal data held in disease registries/health information systems must therefore comply with one of the legal grounds and specific derogations listed in Article 9 of the GDPR for the lawful processing of this special category of personal data as well as with the core principles set out in Article 5.

Table 1 below presents the exemptions (i.e. the legitimate legal bases) for processing health related data in registries/HIS.

Among the GDPR legitimate purposes for the processing of sensitive data that are relevant for health, two broad categories can be distinguished:

- Primary purposes, i.e. when the processing is necessary for the provision of health and social care;
- Secondary purposes, i.e. when the processing is carried out for further purposes not previously identified (e.g. EHRs data used for research, for public health, for health system monitoring, etc.).

As highlighted in table 1, although a common legal base for data processing is considered “consent”, Member States may allow the processing of personal and sensitive data for both primary and secondary purposes, also without data subject consent, on the basis of national legislation. The latter must be “proportionate to the aim pursued, respect the essence of the right to data protection and provide for suitable and specific measures to safeguard the fundamental rights and the interests of the data subject”, including professional secrecy where relevant.

Data processing for scientific research or statistical purposes must also be in accordance with Article 89(1); accordingly, data controllers must “ensure that technical and organisational measures are in place in particular in order to ensure respect for the principle of data minimisation”.

In addition, Art. 9(4) allows Member States to “maintain or introduce further conditions, including limitations, with regard to the processing of genetic data, biometric data or data concerning health”.

National regulators can therefore choose among the various interests listed in articles 9 and 6 of the GDPR to put in place further legislation, compliant with the EU legislative framework, that would create a specific legal base for data processing.

Indeed, all EU countries have legislation in force allowing the processing of data for primary purposes using different GDPR options. Moreover, data collection for the care of patients is generally seen as part of the care itself and is protected by professional secrecy and confidentiality rules. The same applies to data processing necessary for the management of health or social care systems and services, which are strictly linked and functional to the care of patients.

The scenario is completely different for the secondary use of data, which is not directly linked to the care of patients but rather to wider societal benefits. In this case, several countries have adopted a more stringent interpretation of data protection requirements and have not (or only partially) used the possibilities ex Art 9 (2) and 9 (4) of the GDPR to enact further legislation enabling data processing e.g. for disease registries/HIS functions¹¹.

The different legal bases used to process data in disease registries/HIS across European countries and the stringent interpretation of the GDPR requirements in some EU countries have substantially limited the possibility of sharing health information both within countries and across Europe, including the possibility of performing data linkage operations¹².

A recent EU assessment of EU MS rules on health data highlighted that the use of data for wider public health and health systems purposes is limited in many EU countries due to legislative barriers, in particular to data protection laws¹³.

To overcome these issues, the EHDS Proposal of Regulation is trying to harmonise health data processing in the EU, while ensuring GDPR compliance (see section 4). The recently approved text, for example, includes rules on opting out that build a good balance between respecting patients’ wishes and ensuring that the right data is available to the right people for the public interest.

Table 1: Exceptions ex Article 9 of the GDPR relevant to disease registries/HIS

<i>Legal base (Exceptions to general prohibition of processing sensitive data)</i>		<i>Requirements (Conditions for data processing within each legal base)</i>
Art 9.2 (a)	Data subject has given explicit consent to the processing of personal health data.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explicit consent must be for one or more specified purposes.
Art 9.2 (g)	Processing is necessary for reasons of substantial public interest.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Processing is allowed on the basis of Union or Member State law: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> □ which shall be proportionate to the aim pursued; □ respect the essence of the right to data protection; and □ provide for suitable and specific measures to safeguard the fundamental rights and the interests of the data subject.
Art 9.2 (h)	Processing is necessary <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • for the purposes of preventive or occupational medicine; • medical diagnosis; • the provision of health or social care or treatment; or • the management of health or social care systems and services. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Processing is allowed on the basis of Union or Member State law or • Pursuant to contract with a health professional subject to the conditions and safeguards referred to in paragraph 9. 3, i.e.: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> □ data are processed by or under the responsibility of a professional subject to the obligation of professional secrecy under Union or Member State law.
Art 9.2 (i)	Processing is necessary for reasons of public interest in the area of public health, such as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • protecting against serious cross-border threats to health; or • ensuring high standards of quality and safety of health care and of medicinal products or medical devices. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Processing is allowed on the basis of Union or Member State law, <ul style="list-style-type: none"> □ which provides for suitable and specific measures to safeguard the rights and freedoms of the data subject, in particular professional secrecy.
Art 9.2 (j)	Processing is necessary: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • for archiving purposes in the public interest; • scientific or historical research purposes; or • statistical purposes. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Processing is allowed in accordance with safeguards of Article 89(1): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> □ technical and organisational measures are in place in particular in order to ensure respect for the principle of data minimisation; □ those measures may include (if those purposes can be fulfilled in that manner): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ pseudonymisation or ✓ anonymisation. • Processing is allowed based on Union or Member State law: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> □ which shall be proportionate to the aim pursued; □ respect the essence of the right to data protection;and □ provide for suitable and specific measures to safeguard the fundamental rights and the interests of the data subject.
Art 9. 4	Member States may maintain or introduce further conditions, including limitations, with regard to the processing of genetic data, biometric or health data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MS can enact further sectoral legislation (lex specialis) on these matters, in compliance with the GDPR.

3.2.2 Data subjects rights

The GDPR recognises the following data subject rights:

- The right to information on the data processing operations concerning them;
- The right of data access;
- The right to rectification;
- The right to erasure or to be forgotten;
- The right to restriction of the processing of personal data;
- The right to data portability;
- The right to object at any time to the processing of personal data;
- The right to avoid automated decision-making, including profiling.

Data controllers are responsible and accountable for adherence to data subjects' rights; and this extends to data processors and to any other data controller to whom data are transferred.

Adherence to the rights of data subjects is of utmost importance in the context of disease registries/HIS, as such compliance leads to fostering citizens' trust in the processing activities and, as a consequence, to their willingness to provide their data.

Table 2 summarises the main requirements and possible measures of implementation of data subjects' rights in disease registries/HIS.

3.2.3 Data subjects' rights under the EHDS Regulation

The EHDS Regulation complements and extends the right to access, rectification, restriction, portability and to object to the priority categories of personal electronic health data for primary use indicated in article 5 (i.e. patient summaries; electronic prescriptions; electronic dispensations; medical imaging studies and related imaging reports; medical test results, including laboratory and other diagnostic results and related reports; discharge reports).

These rights will have to be exercised via an electronic health data access service, which should provide an immediate answer (e.g. data should be directly downloadable from the electronic health data access service). Nevertheless, rights under Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR) should still apply; for example, the right to obtain a paper copy of the electronic health data will remain, as this is one of the rights provided by the GDPR.

It is worth noting that the right to data portability envisaged by the GDPR is limited to data processing based on consent or contract and provided by the data subject to a controller. Additionally, the right to have the personal data transmitted directly from one controller to another can be exercised only where it is technically feasible; and data controllers do not have an obligation to make it technically feasible. Hence, the right to data portability envisaged by the GDPR has, de facto, a limited applicability.

The right to data portability envisaged in the EHDS Regulation complements and expands the one envisaged by the GDPR by ensuring that data subjects can transmit their electronic health data, including inferred data, in the European electronic health record exchange format, irrespective of the legal basis for processing the electronic health data. In the context of the EHDS, data controllers have an obligation to ensure data portability. Hence, disease registries/information systems linked to EHR systems should guarantee this right.

<https://www.inf-act.eu/>

Table 2: Data subjects rights

Data Subject rights	Main Requirements	Measures for implementation
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Right to information 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Controllers must take appropriate measures to provide any information and any communication relating to processing to the data subject. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Established procedures are in place to provide information and communications to data subjects.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Right to access • Right to rectification • Right to erasure (if registries/HIS data are collected with data subject consent) • Right to data portability (when data processing is based on consent) • Right to object (if registries/HIS data are collected with data subject consent) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Controllers must facilitate the exercise of data subject rights; • Controllers must not refuse to act on the request of the data subject for exercising his or her rights. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The information system allows patients to exercise their rights through functionalities/on line requests that: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ grant patients access to their data and allow updates, rectifications, erasures, etc.; ○ include a system for the request and provision of information and communications between controllers and patients; ○ allow patients to manage the conditions for data sharing and the secondary use of their data through opt in or opt out solutions/buttons; ○ collect and store data using interoperable formats to ensure data portability.

3.2.4 Accountability

According to the GDPR, data controllers and processors are legally responsible and must be able to demonstrate compliance of their processing operations with data protection laws.

The accountability requirement imposes the necessity of data controllers and processors to implement appropriate technical and organisational measures to promote and safeguard data protection in their processing activities, including the effectiveness of the measures (i.e. measures must be reviewed and updated when necessary).

Art 24 of the GDPR specifies that those measures must include the implementation of appropriate data protection policies by the controller.

The GDPR contains a list of technical and organisational measures that controllers and processors should use to demonstrate compliance with the Regulation's obligations i.e.

- Maintain records of the processing activities;
- Appoint a data protection officer (DPO), if required;

- Conduct a data protection impact assessment (DPIA) for processing operation that are likely to pose high risks to the rights and freedoms of individuals.

3.2.5 Records of processing activities

Art 30 of the GDPR envisages that the controller is responsible for maintaining a record of processing activities in writings, including in digital format. It further specifies the content of the record, which has to include:

- The controller details (i.e. name and contact details of the controller, joint controller, controller's representative and of the DPO, if nominated);
- The purposes of the processing;
- A description of the categories of data subjects and of personal data;
- The categories of recipients of the data;
- Details of transfers to a third country or an international organisation, including the documentation of suitable safeguards;
- The retention periods;
- A description of the technical and organisational security measures.

Each processor will have to maintain a record of processing activities carried out on behalf of a controller.

However, the requirement to keep records does not apply to an enterprise or an organisation employing fewer than 250 persons unless:

- The processing is likely to result in a risk to the rights and freedoms of data subjects;
- The processing is not occasional;
- The processing includes special categories of data.

3.2.6 Data protection officer (DPO)

Data Protection Officers (DPOs) are persons with expert knowledge of data protection law and practices who assist the controller or processor to monitor internal compliance with data protection rules.

According to Art. 37 of the GDPR, DPOs should act independently in the performance of their duties and tasks and may be members of staff internal or external to the controller or processor functions. The contact details of the DPO must be communicated to the supervisory authority and made available to data subjects, who can contact the DPO with regard to all issues related to processing of their personal data and to the exercise of their rights under this Regulation (Art 38).

Consequently, the DPO has a key role acting as an intermediary between the controller or processor, the data subjects and the supervisory authority.

The designation of a data protection officer is required if:

- the processing is carried out by a public authority or body;
- the core activities of the controller or the processor consist of processing operations that require regular and systematic monitoring of data subjects on a large scale;
- the core activities of the controller or the processor consist of processing on a large scale of special categories of data pursuant to Article 9.

Thus, in the deployment of a digital HIS (d-HIS), the nomination of a DPO would be necessary if one of the conditions listed above is met.

3.2.7 Data protection impact assessment (DPIA)

The GDPR envisages detailed controllers' obligations with regard to a data-protection impact assessment (DPIA). ART 35 of the Regulation states that when the processing involves new technologies that could result in high risk to the rights and freedoms of natural persons, DPIA has to be carried out prior of processing.

DPIA is mandatory, among other things, when the processing involves special categories (or "sensitive") of data on a large scale.

Art 29 Working Party has issued guidelines on data-protection impact assessment¹⁴, which have been endorsed by the European Data Protection Board¹⁵. According to the Guidelines, the following factors should be considered when determining whether the processing is carried out on a large scale:

- The number of data subjects concerned, either as a specific number or as a proportion of the relevant population;
- The volume of data and/or the range of different data items being processed;
- The duration, or permanence, of the data processing activity;
- The geographical extent of the processing activity.

Matching or combining datasets is also considered an element that can potentially involve high-risk processing.

The setting up of disease registries/HIS often combine all the elements that render the DPIA mandatory:

- The processing involves new technologies that could result in high risk;
- The processing involves the processing on a large scale of special categories or "sensitive" data;
- The processing involves matching or combining datasets.

The GDPR does not provide indications on the DPIA methodology, although it does list some minimum requirements, namely that it should contain:

- A systematic description of processing operations and purposes of the processing;
- An assessment of the necessity and proportionality of the processing operations in relation to the purposes;
- An assessment of the risks to the rights and freedoms of data subjects;
- The measures envisaged to address the risks, including safeguards, security measures and mechanisms to ensure the protection of personal data and to demonstrate compliance with this Regulation.

The ART 29 Working Party Guidelines make reference to some broad DPIAs frameworks developed by the French Commission Nationale d'Informatique et des libertés (CNIL)¹⁶ and the UK Information Commissioner's Office (ICO)¹⁷ to provide examples on how to carry out a DPIA, but none of them is specific for the health sector, which leaves a degree of uncertainty on how to develop them in the context of health information systems.

There are a few examples in the literature of DPIA methodology in the field of health information systems, from which insights and best practices could be drawn¹⁸⁻¹⁹.

Table 3 below summarises the accountability requirements for data controllers of disease registries and health information systems identified in section 3.8.

Table 3: Accountability Requirements

Accountability Elements	Accountability Requirements
<i>Records of processing activities</i>	<p>Controllers and processors records must contain:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The controller details; • The purposes of the processing; • A description of the categories of data subjects and of personal data; • The categories of recipients of the data; • Details of transfers to a third country or an international organisation, including the documentation of suitable safeguards; • The retention periods; • A description of the technical and organisational security measures.
<i>Data protection officer (DPO)</i>	<p>Designation of DPO is required if:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The processing is carried out by a public authority or body; • The core activities of the controller or the processor consist of processing operations that require regular and systematic monitoring of data subjects on a large scale; • The core activities of the controller or the processor consist of processing on a large scale of special categories of data pursuant to Article 9. <p><i>The DPO should:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Have expert knowledge of data protection law and practices; • Assist the controller or processor to monitor internal compliance with data protection rules; • Perform the tasks indicated in Art 39 of GDP independently; • Provide his/her contact details; which must be: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> □ communicated to the supervisory authority; □ made available to data subjects.
<i>Data protection impact assessment</i>	<p>Is required when:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The processing involves new technologies that could result in high risk; • The processing involves the processing on a large scale of special categories or “sensitive” of data; • the processing involves matching or combining datasets. <p>Minimum requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Systematic description of processing operations and purposes of the processing; • Assessment of the necessity and proportionality of the processing operations in relation to the purposes; • Assessment of the risks to the rights and freedoms of data subjects; • Measures envisaged to address the risks, including safeguards, security measures and mechanisms to ensure the protection of personal data and to demonstrate compliance with this Regulation. <p>Methodology:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No specific indications; • Few examples exist specific on health information systems.

3.2.8 Security requirements under the GDPR

The security of data processing is another crucial principle of the GDPR.

Art. 5.1 (f) of the GDPR states that personal data have to be: processed in a manner that ensures appropriate security of the personal data, including protection against unauthorised or unlawful processing and against accidental loss, destruction or damage, using appropriate technical or organisational measures (“integrity and confidentiality”). Hence, security refers to data integrity and confidentiality.

Controllers must implement technical and organisational measures that ensure a level of security appropriate to the risks that are presented by the processing (Art. 32 GDPR). These technical and organisational measures include security measures (e.g. anonymisation, pseudonymisation, encryption, authentication etc.) that controllers should implement, by design and by default, to comply with the Regulation. Accordingly, controllers:

- Have the obligation to determine, prior to starting a processing activity, whether the purpose of processing can be achieved by using pseudonymised or anonymised data;
- Must assess the severity and likelihood of the risks for data subjects in order to implement the security measures that are proportionate to the risks at a stake (taking into account the state of the art, the costs of implementation and the nature, scope, context and purposes of processing; i.e. balancing efforts against the risks to data subjects).

Conducting a DPIA is a way of carrying out such a risk assessment, when the conditions for its use are in place (e.g. new technologies, large-scale data processing of sensitive data, high risks are involved).

According to Art 32, controllers are also obliged:

- To set up a process for regularly testing, assessing and evaluating the effectiveness of technical and organisational measures for ensuring the security of the processing. This process should be documented in the security policy;
- To ensure the ongoing confidentiality, integrity, availability and resilience of processing systems and services;
- To restore the availability and access to personal data in a timely manner in the event of a physical or technical incident.

According to Art. 33 and 34, controllers are obliged to notify personal data breaches, without undue delay, to the supervisory authority, unless the personal data breach is unlikely to result in a risk to the rights and freedoms of natural persons, as well as communicate the personal data breach to the data subject.

The following subsections deep in the security measures envisaged in the GDPR; i.e.:

- Data protection by design and by default;
- Data protection engineering;
- Data breach notification and reporting.

3.2.9 Data protection by design and by default

Disease registries/HIS data processing are normally considered high-risk data processing as a consequence of the large amounts of data processed and their sensitivity. Hence, data controllers must ensure that privacy and data protection issues are appropriately considered at the architectural design stage of the registry/HIS and security measures maintained and updated throughout its life-cycle.

Data protection by design builds directly from the elements of a DPIA or equivalent risk assessment. It implies that privacy-enhancing human, organisational and technological measures are designed from the beginning and built in the registry/HIS to avoid ex post issues of non-compliance, as well as routinely updated during the data processing life-cycle.

Data controllers must also ensure that data protection by default requirements are met by ensuring that only data necessary to achieve the intended and stated purposes are processed (data minimisation). Systems built on the concept of ‘data protection by default’ are designed such that their initial settings and behaviours are to safeguard the protection of data (e.g. by denying data access) in the event of an error or unexpected scenario.

Table 4 below illustrates the elements to be taken into account to fulfil privacy-by-design requirements.

Table 4: Privacy-by-Design Requirements

Privacy-by-design Elements	Privacy-by-Design Requirements
<p>Controllers are obliged to implement appropriate technical and organisational measures and necessary safeguards into the processing since the early stage of development of the information system.</p>	<p>These measures and safeguards can be any method or means that a controller may employ in the processing; e.g.:</p> <p><u>Organisational Measures:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Allowing access to data only to authorised staff, bound by professional secrecy or with a confidentiality duty; • Training employees about basic “cyber hygiene”; • Obligating processors contractually to implement specific data minimisation practices, etc. <p><u>Technical Measures:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pseudonymisation; • Anonymisation; • Malware detection systems; • Privacy and information security management systems. <p>Standards, best practices and codes of conduct that are recognised by associations and other bohttps://www.inf-act.eu/dies representing categories of controllers should be used for determining appropriate measures.</p>
<p>Element to be taken into account:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • State of the art (dynamic); • Costs of implementation; • Nature, scope and purposes of processing. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • State of the art is dynamic and must be regularly checked; • Costs of implementation should not be dis-proportional; • Nature, scope and purposes of processing must be evaluated in relation to the risks and severity for the rights and freedoms of the data subject (risk-based approach/risk assessment).
<p>Time aspect:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • At the time of the determination of the means for processing (system architecture design); • At the time of the processing itself (maintenance and review of data protection/security requirements during the life-cycle of the information system)

Table 5 illustrates the elements to be taken into account to fulfil privacy-by-default requirements, as well as the measures for implementation.

Table 5: Privacy-by-Default Requirements

Privacy-by-default Elements	Privacy-by-Default Requirements
By default, controllers must implement appropriate measures to ensure that only personal data which are necessary for the specific purposes are processed.	<p><u>Organisational Measures:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification of the data necessary for the processing, of the purposes, retention period and the accessibility conditions. <p><u>Technical Measures</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inclusion of systems/services/functionalities that minimise data collection and use by default; e.g. Software applications, computer programs or devices that have a default setting (through choosing pre-existing or preselected values of a configurable setting) that minimise data collection and use.
<p>This obligation applies to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Amount of personal data collected; • Extent of the processing; • Storage period; • Accessibility. 	<p>The information system should include functionalities that by default:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limit the amount of personal data collected to what is necessary for the specific purposes (data minimisation); • Limit the extent of the processing to what is necessary for the defined purposes (purpose specification); • Limit the storage period (storage limitation) to what is necessary for achieving the processing purposes(e.g. systems for automatic periodic data deletion); • Limit the data accessibility as to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▫ Prevent unauthorised access; ▫ Limit access to only necessary and trained staff, bound by professional secrecy and confidentiality obligations.

3.2.10 Data Protection Engineering

According to ENISA (the European Union Agency for Cybersecurity), data protection engineering is part of data-protection-by-design and -by-default. It supports the selection, deployment and configuration of appropriate security measures, both technical and organisational, in order to satisfy data protection principles and protect data subjects’ rights and freedoms²⁰. Examples of data protection engineering are anonymisation and pseudonymisation techniques.

Anonymisation is considered in the GDPR as a security measure to be used wherever possible and when the identification of data subject is no longer necessary. Recital 26 of the GDPR defines anonymous information, as “...information which does not relate to an identified or identifiable natural person or to personal data rendered anonymous in such a manner that the data subject is not or no longer identifiable”. Hence, anonymous data is not personal data and does not fall under the GDPR rules.

Data anonymisation is achieved by altering the data, either by introducing noise or by generalising the values of certain fields. The more extensive the modifications to the original dataset, the lower is the re-identification possibility; which however does have a negative impact on data utility.

Amongst the most used techniques there are K-anonymisation and differential privacy.

K-anonymity combines sets of data with similar attributes, this way identifying information on any of the individuals included in the dataset can be obscured; i.e. the information relative to a data subject cannot be distinguished from at least k-1 data subjects included in the same dataset²¹.

Differential privacy is based on the modification of data via the addition of randomness or noise, thereby allowing studies on larger statistical trends in a dataset without revealing individual data. The greater the noise, the better is the privacy protection against the risk of re-identification; however, increasing noise inevitably lowers data accuracy²².

It has to be noted that the selection of most appropriate anonymisation techniques should be made on a case-by-case basis, as it ultimately depends on the type of data, the acceptable risk of re-identification and performance degradation levels²³. Sometimes a mixture of generalisation and the introduction of noise is adopted across the various fields in a data set. The introduction of additional privacy enhancing technologies is sometimes also necessary even when state-of-the-art anonymisation techniques are used, as residual risks of re-identification may still materialise. The protective measures adopted should be proportional to the risk of re-identification, and will need to take into account the specificities of different data categories or of different anonymisation or aggregation techniques.

Ex Art 4(5) of the GDPR, Pseudonymisation means “the processing of personal data in such a manner that the personal data can no longer be attributed to a specific data subject without the use of additional information, provided that such additional information is kept separately and is subject to technical and organisational measures to ensure that the personal data are not attributed to an identified or identifiable natural person”.

Pseudonymisation is a particularly suitable technique for registries/HIS as it allows re-identification of data subjects when necessary, which greatly facilitates data linkage allowing information to be used for improved care of patients, health monitoring and surveillance, epidemiological research, etc.

The most common pseudonymisation techniques used in healthcare include:

- Counter: Monotonic counter which starts at a certain value and is increased each time a new pseudonym is necessary;
- Random number: Random value extracted between a minimum and a maximum boundary each time a new pseudonym is necessary;
- Hash function: One-way (non-reversible) cryptographic function transforming input personal data in fixed-length values;
- Hash-based message authentication code (HMAC): One-way (non-reversible) cryptographic function adding a key that makes it less predictable than a hash function;
- Encryption: Two-way (reversible) cryptographic function transforming an input personal data in values that can be re-transformed in its original format using a key²⁴.

However, the appropriateness of pseudonymisation techniques also depends on the type of data and should be evaluated case by case. In addition, the pseudonymisation policy implemented is also important to choose the most suitable technique.

The policies to be implemented can be:

- Deterministic pseudonymisation – always using the same pseudonym for the same data;
- Document randomised pseudonymisation – using the same pseudonym for the same data only within a consistent scope;

- Fully randomised pseudonymisation – always using a different pseudonym for the same data²⁵.

The European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA) has issued several reports on these techniques that can be used to implement, by design and by default, appropriate technical and organisational security measures²⁶.

Table 6 highlights the security requirements with regard to data protection engineering.

Table 6: Data Protection Engineering Requirements

Security Measure	Main requirements	Means of Implementation
Anonymisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Altering the data, either by introducing noise or by generalising the values of certain fields. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • K-anonymisation; • Differential privacy.
Pseudonymisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal data can no longer be attributed to a specific data subject without the use of additional information (re-identification key); • Such additional information is kept separately and subject to appropriate technical and organisational measures. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Counter: Monotonic counter which starts at a certain value and is increased each time a new pseudonym is necessary; • Random number: Random value extracted between a minimum and a maximum boundary each time a new pseudonym is necessary; • Hash function: One-way (non-reversible) cryptographic function transforming input personal data in fixed-length values; • Hash-based message authentication code (HMAC): One-way (non-reversible) cryptographic function adding a key that makes it less predictable than a hash function; • Encryption: Two-way (reversible) cryptographic function transforming an input personal data in values that can be re-transformed in its original format using a key.

3.2.11 Data Breaches Notification

According to Article 4 (12) of the GDPR “personal data breach” means a breach of security leading to the accidental or unlawful destruction, loss, alteration, unauthorised disclosure of, or access to, personal data transmitted, stored or otherwise processed.

Article 33 of the GDPR requires controllers to report personal data security breaches to the competent supervisory authority when they are likely to result in a risk to the rights and freedoms of data subjects.

In such cases, the data controller has to report the breach without undue delay and, where feasible, not later than 72 hours after becoming aware of it, unless it is possible to demonstrate that the personal data breach is unlikely to result in a risk to the rights and freedoms of natural persons. With regard to processors, they are in turn obliged to notify the controller without undue delay after becoming aware of a personal data breach.

The notification to the supervisory authority must:

- Describe the nature of the personal data breach including where possible, the categories and approximate number of data subjects concerned and the categories and approximate number of personal data records concerned;
- Communicate the name and contact details of the data protection officer or other contact point where more information can be obtained;
- Describe the likely consequences of the personal data breach;
- Describe the measures taken or proposed to be taken by the controller to address the personal data breach, including, where appropriate, measures to mitigate its possible adverse effects.

Ex Art 34 of the GDPR, when the personal data breach is likely to result in a high risk to the rights and freedoms of natural persons, the controller has to communicate the personal data breach also to the data subject, without undue delay.

However, the controller is exempted by this obligation if:

- Appropriate technical and organisational measures have been implemented in order to protect the data subject's personal data (e.g. data were encrypted);
- Subsequent measures have been taken to ensure that any high risk to the rights and freedoms of the data subject is no longer expected to materialise;
- It would involve disproportionate effort. In such a case, a public communication or similar measures would be sufficient.

Consequently, when controllers become aware of a data breach, they should first assess the level of risk to data subjects that could result from the data breach in order to ascertain if the notification to the supervisory authority and the communication to data subjects are required, as well as to implement the most appropriate mitigation measures²⁷.

This risk is considered existing when the breach may lead to physical, material or non-material damage for the individuals such as loss of control over their personal data or limitation of their rights, discrimination, identity theft or fraud, financial loss, unauthorised reversal of pseudonymisation, damage to reputation, loss of confidentiality of personal data protected by professional secrecy or any other significant economic or social disadvantage to the natural person concerned (Recital 85 of the GDPR). Hence, when the data breach involves sensitive data, as in the case of health institutions processing, e.g. electronic health records (EHRs), such damage should be considered likely to occur.

Infringements of the provision included in Articles 33 and 34 can lead to administrative fines up to €10.000.000, or in the case of an undertaking, up to 2% of the total worldwide annual turnover of the preceding financial year, whichever is higher (Art. 83 of the GDPR).

3.2.12 Procedures for the handling and management of data breaches: Business Continuity, Disaster recovery and Resilience

In order to avoid sanctions and demonstrate compliance with security requirements, controllers should establish the procedures for the handling and management of data breaches.

As good practice, controllers can establish an internal register of breaches, including information on the event and the subsequent mitigation measures implemented; which would help demonstrating compliance with security and accountability requirements²⁸.

According to Art. 32.1 (b), the technical and organisational measures that controllers and processors must implement must ensure:

- The resilience of processing systems and services;
- The ability to restore the availability and access to personal data in a timely manner in the event of a physical or technical incident.
- In order to fulfil these obligations, the following measures could be adopted:
- Incident Response Plan; which defines the procedures for the reporting of the breaches to competent authorities and data subjects, as well as the possible mitigation actions and measures;
- Business Continuity Plan; which establishes the procedures and technical measures to be followed to ensure continuity and availability of the processing system in the event of personal data breaches or incidents;
- Disaster Recovery Plan; which seeks to restore appropriate access to information after a major calamity

There are no unique methodologies to implement these plans as they can vary according to the data processing, data type, risks, etc. Nevertheless, the use of ISO standards can be considered an appropriate means that controllers and processors can use to comply with GDPR security requirements; e.g.:

- ISO 27001:2013 – A.5 Security policy
- ISO 27001:2013 – A.9.1.1 Access control policy
- ISO 27001:2013 – A.16 Information security incident management
- ISO 27001:2013 – A.17 Information security aspects of business continuity management
- ISO 27001:2013 – A.12.3 Back-Up
- ISO 27001:2013 – A.12.6 Technical vulnerability management

Table 7 illustrates the obligations and measures for the implementation of data breaches requirements, as well as the Procedures for the handling and management of data breaches.

Table 7: Data Breach Requirements

Data Breach Elements	Requirements
<p>Controllers must report personal data security breaches to the competent supervisory authority:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • if the data breach is likely to result in a risk to the rights and freedoms of data subjects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assessment of the risk to the rights and freedoms of data subject; • Data controller must report the breach without undue delay and, where feasible, not later than 72 hours after becoming aware of it.
<p>Controllers must communicate the personal data breach to the data subject</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • if the data breach is likely to result in a risk to the rights and freedoms of data subjects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assessment of the risk to the rights and freedoms of data subject; • Data controller must communicate the breach to the data subject without undue delay.
<p>Procedures for the handling and management of data breaches:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incident Response Plan; • Business Continuity Plan; • Disaster Recovery Plan; • ISO standards.

3.3 Data Governance

While the GDPR provides a common foundation for data protection in the EU, enhancing the effectiveness of secondary use and processing of data held in disease registries and health information systems necessitates the establishment of compatible health-data governance frameworks and arrangements. The latter are essential to leverage fully the possibilities offered by EHDS and ensure the availability of, access to and sharing of health data across Member States.

There is no single common definition for health data governance, but different organisations agree that data governance refers to diverse technical, policy, regulatory or institutional/organisational arrangements to build trust and enable the harnessing of individual and collective benefits from health data, while addressing possible associated risks and challenges.

To assist governments in achieving appropriate data governance, the 2016 OECD Council Recommendation on Health Data Governance²⁹ (OECD Recommendation) provides a comprehensive guidance for building national data governance frameworks based on high-level principles and best practices. It aims to respond to the growing need for a consensus about the conditions within which health data can be appropriately governed to enable health data processing to take place both domestically and transnationally so that more countries can use health data for research, statistics and healthcare quality improvement.

The OECD Recommendation sets out 12 key high-level principles, largely aimed at reinforcing trust in data systems and harmonising processes and practices. Specifically, according to the OECD Recommendation, health data governance frameworks should provide for:

- Engagement and participation of stakeholders in the development of a national health data governance framework;
- Co-ordination within government and co-operation among organisations processing personal health data to encourage common data-related policies and standards;
- Reviews of the capacity of public sector health data systems to serve and protect public interests;
- Clear provision of information to individuals about the processing of their personal health data including notification of any significant data breach or misuse;
- The processing of personal health data by informed consent and appropriate alternatives;
- The implementation of review and approval procedures to process personal health data for research and other health-related engine purposes;
- Transparency through public information about the purposes for processing of personal health data and approval criteria;
- Maximising the development and use of technology for data processing and data protection;
- Mechanisms to monitor and evaluate the impact of the national health data governance framework, including health data availability, policies and practices to manage privacy, protection of personal health data and digital security risks;
- Training and skills development of personal health data processors;
- Implementation of controls and safeguards within organisations processing personal health data including technological, physical and organisational measures designed to protect privacy and digital security;
- Requiring that organisations processing personal health data demonstrate that they meet the expectations set out in the national health data governance framework.

3.3.1 State of implementation of data governance in disease registries across EU Countries

Key elements of health data governance as set out by the above 12 principles work in harmony with the GDPR and are largely covered by the legal requirements listed in previous paragraphs.

The capacity of public sector disease registry systems to serve and protect the public interest, reduce the burden of major NCDs and improve citizens' health and well-being requires, however, additional data governance conditions, policies and practices, which are briefly reviewed below. These conditions are further reflected in the requirements set out by the EHDS Regulation discussed in later sections.

3.3.2 Data quality and utility (availability, population coverage, time period and fitness for use)

In order to increase the effectiveness of the secondary use of health data, and to fully benefit from the possibilities offered by secondary use, datasets held in disease registries and HIS need to be available. Such datasets should be accessible, timely, of high quality, ready and suitable or fit for the purpose of creating scientific, innovative and societal value and quality as possible. These elements are also listed as key features of the Health Data Quality and Utility Label envisaged in article 56 of the EHDS Regulation.

According to a recent OECD survey, several issues have been identified concerning data quality and utility.

Although many countries' NCDs datasets cover 100% of the target population; there are yet important exceptions. The most common reason why national datasets do not cover the full population is because there are missing records for care provided by private sector providers and institutions, or that are covered by private insurance. In some cases, healthcare datasets are based on a representative sample of the target population. Voluntary participation of healthcare providers or drawing data from a network of participants is also a reason for incomplete coverage of national data sets. Some countries also have exclusions for patients in certain regions or have datasets that target a sub-set of patients or providers.

In addition, it has been reported that only in a few countries datasets rely to some extent on data extracted automatically from electronic health records; while in most countries available key national healthcare datasets have some mixture of data entry from paper records and data extracted automatically from electronic records. Nevertheless, the benefits of automatic data extraction include improvements in timeliness of data capture, avoidance of costs associated with paper data capture, and minimisation of errors that occur from transcription of information.

As discussed in previous sections, it is also crucial that the types of data collected, data formats and coding systems are harmonised among the different silos of information and across registries to allow within countries and cross-border optimal use of information and interoperability. In most countries, data coding within national datasets is being carried out by both health professionals and clinicians.

Finally, direct linkage is theoretically possible when personal record or other identifiers of interest are available. However, the use of a common unique identifier directly to link personal data is, as noted, often limited because either it does not exist, or it is not regularly used, or it is recorded incorrectly.

3.3.3 Review and approval processes for personal health data processing

In most EU countries, organisations can create datasets and can undertake dataset linkages under the precondition that their activities meet the requirements of the GDPR. Most countries have a data controller within the data custodian's offices for all of their national healthcare datasets. Data

controllers are obliged to implement appropriate technical and organisational measures and necessary safeguards for data processing from the early stage of development of the health data set or information system.

On the other hand, according to the EHDS Regulation, each member state will also need to set up a health-data access body for granting access to data by researchers, companies, or institutions using a decentralised EU-infrastructure (HealthData@EU), which will be established to support cross-border projects³⁰.

Review and approval procedures generally involve an assessment of whether the processing is: within the public interest; robust; objective and fair; timely; promoting consistency in outcomes; transparent while protecting legitimate interests; and supported by an independent multi-disciplinary review.

According to the 2019 OECD survey, several EU countries have already established a central authority responsible for the approval of requests to process personal health data.

Denmark, for example, has established the Danish Health Data Authority. In Belgium, the Information Security Committee is responsible for approving requests to process personal health data; in Luxembourg, the National Commission for Data Protection grants approvals; and in France the data protection authority (CNIL) approves the creation of datasets and the processing of health data. In the Netherlands, organisations can create datasets and can undertake dataset linkages under the precondition that their activities meet the requirements of the GDPR and the Medical Treatment Act. The Data Protection Authority evaluates whether datasets meet GDPR requirements. Further guidelines regarding necessary elements of quality registries are also provided by the national body overseeing the electronic health record system (NICTIZ).

A contributing factor to whether or not dataset linkages are conducted regularly relates to the number of custodians of key national health data sets. Most countries have 3 to 5 different organisations in custody of their key health datasets. As an illustration, in Ireland and the Netherlands there are nine different organisations in custody of key national datasets and in France there are seven different organisations. Countries with multiple custodians have considerably higher challenges integrating and linking data across the pathway of care than in other countries, as legislation and policies governing health data accessibility and sharing would need to be considered and applied across multiple organisations.

3.3.4 Health professionals' training in data protection, data access controls, data de-identification, risk management.

The OECD recommends that countries implement national health-data governance frameworks that establish, among the other things, training and skill development in privacy and data security measures in order to ensure processing of personal health data is in line with prevailing standards and data-processing techniques.

The same is recommended in the EHDS under article 59 and highlighted in WHO's tool-kit on strengthening health information systems³¹; in particular, data governance initiatives should aim to:

- Develop policies, procedures and standards that support data governance efforts;
- Educate all members of the organisation about the importance of data governance and how they can support it.

The 2019/20 OECD survey asked respondents if the organisations responsible for key national healthcare datasets provided regular training to staff regarding their responsibilities to protect privacy and data security. Sixteen countries reported that regular training was provided to staff across all of the organisations responsible for all key healthcare datasets.

In Belgium, the Czech Republic, and Latvia training is provided at the time staff start a new job and then annually afterwards. Slovenia provides training at the time staff start a new job and then every 3-4 years afterwards. In Luxembourg, training is provided at the time staff start a new job and then on an ad hoc basis afterwards. Training is provided annually in Denmark.

Training is provided to new staff and to all staff annually for some healthcare datasets in Estonia (cancer registry, cardiovascular disease registry and mortality data) and for the cancer registry in Japan. Training is provided in Germany for staff processing hospital in-patient data at 1–2-yearly intervals.

France requires training take place before data access can be approved.

3.3.5 Transparency with the public about data processing.

The OECD Recommendation for countries to establish and implement national health-data governance frameworks promotes transparency through public information mechanisms that do not compromise health data privacy or security protections or organisations' commercial or other legitimate interests. Public information should include the following: the purpose of the processing; the health-related public interest served; the legal basis for the processing; the procedure and criteria used to approve the processing; a summary of approval decisions taken; and information about the implementation of the national framework and how effective it has been.

Transparency is important for protecting individuals' privacy and autonomy while also ensuring that data processors and data users are aware of the authority under which data may be used resulting in greater clarity for the performance and planning of health-data-related research programmes.

Twenty-one countries reported in the 2019-20 OECD survey that for all or most key healthcare datasets there is a publicly available description of the purpose and schema of the dataset and most provide a web-link to this public information.

In most countries the description of all or most healthcare datasets includes the health-related public interests served by the data and the legal basis for the processing. The procedure to request access to the data and the criteria used to approve access to the data are also publicly available for all or most healthcare datasets in a majority of countries.

Under the EHDS, health-data access bodies should ensure transparency of secondary use by providing public information (e.g. via biennial activity reports) concerning: the permits granted and their justification; the measures taken to protect the rights of natural persons; how natural persons can exercise their rights in relation to secondary use; and the outcomes of secondary use, such as links to scientific publications. Where appropriate, the information on the outcomes of secondary use should also include a lay summary to be provided by the health-data user. These transparency obligations complement the obligations laid down in Article 14 of the GDPR.

3.3.6 Standard data sharing agreements

Data sharing agreements are for the purpose of: setting out the purpose of the data sharing; addressing what happens to the data at each stage; setting standards; and helping all the parties involved in sharing to be clear about their roles and responsibilities. Having a data-sharing agreement in place helps demonstrate that an organisation is meets its accountability obligations under the GDPR.

Seven EU countries (Belgium, Denmark, Finland, Netherlands, Luxembourg, Slovenia, Sweden) reported in the 2019-20 OECD survey that for all or most of their national key healthcare datasets there is a requirement of having a data sharing agreement.

Examples of the requirements for data privacy and security practices in standard data sharing agreements include:

- Qualified personnel;
- Secure data storage;
- Data use in accordance with applicable laws;
- Data used only for approved purposes;
- Secure physical site where data is held;
- Data access restricted via a secure server (remote access);
- Data access restricted to authorised staff;
- Data destruction date respected;
- No unauthorised data linkages;
- No unauthorised data sharing;
- No attempt at data re-identification;
- Disclosure rules applied to published statistics and research findings;
- Training in data privacy and security protection;
- Adherence to national or international standards for IT security

3.4 Data protection and data governance: best practices in data linkage

As data linkage in disease registries/HIS normally constitutes a secondary use of sensitive data, the GDPR requirements previously presented must be met, in particular:

- A valid legal base for the data linkage must be in place;
- Patients rights must be guaranteed;
- Accountability for the processing operation must be ensured through:
 - Keeping records of processing activities
 - Consulting the Data Protection Officer (DPO)
 - Carrying out a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA); which is required when the processing involves matching or combining datasets
- Security Requirements must be met.

Nevertheless, best practices in data linkage involve the use of privacy-protective methods and techniques that are aimed to fulfil GDPR requirements while allowing data use for the scope of data linkage.

In the context of the BRIDGE-Health Project³², sponsored by the European Commission, a survey among three European consortia accessing large amounts of sensitive data from disease registries on a routine bases was conducted to identify aspects such as compliance of data linkage operations with the GDPR. The survey results were mostly heterogeneous, highlighting an overall poor compliance of the sample with privacy/data protection principles. The assessment tool also identified the privacy protective practices in data linkage, which are as follows:

- To use a unique personal identifiers for data linkages;
- To use standard practices for creating pseudonyms from direct identifiers;
- To use standard practices for deleting direct identifiers (such as names and patient numbers) for the performance of data linkages;

- To use a standard process for the assessment of the risk of data re-identification;
- To document the de-identification and/or pseudonymisation methodology and apply state of the art techniques;
- To use standard practices for the treatment of attributes that pose a re-identification risk (such as rare diseases, exact dates, locations, or ethnic origins).

In addition, data controllers of disease registries/health-databases/HIS should implement appropriate and state-of-the-art data protection engineering techniques, as well as privacy-by-design and by-default methods.

These measures would ensure that organisational and technical measures are appropriate to the scale of the risk posed by the processing operation and compliant with the GDPR.

Finally, data linkage should also adhere to data governance principles and best practices such as:

- Data quality and utility (availability, population coverage, time period and fitness for use);
- Review and approval processes for personal health data processing;
- Health professionals' training in data protection, data access controls, data de-identification, risk management;
- Transparency with the public about data processing;
- Standard data sharing agreements.

These best practices have been fully detailed in section 4.

3.5 Interoperability in the European Health Data Space (EHDS) Regulation

Diabetes registries adopt various ways of collecting data ranging from manual entry to automated data capture from electronic health records, linkage of different national databases or quality registries, or a combination of methods³³.

Data are usually collected from different data sources such as hospital databases, administrative databases, EHRs, health-insurance databases, national statistics offices, etc. Hence, it is crucial that the types of data collected, data formats and coding systems are harmonised among the different silos of information and across registries to allow optimal use of information and interoperability within countries and cross-border.

Currently, the heterogeneous implementation of diabetes registries and data sources hampers the comparability of quality and outcomes across Europe. Legal and administrative constraints also adversely impact the possibility of using relevant health information and of linking data contained in multiple data sources³⁴.

The Proposal for a Regulation on the EHDS was enacted in 2022 with the aim of filling the existing legislative gap relative to health information systems and the exchange of electronic health data. A compromised text was approved by the European Parliament in April 2024³⁵.

The Proposal for an EHDS Regulation could provide a suitable model for overcoming these issues with regard to both the primary use of data (for registries that automatically capture data from EHRs systems and/or use real world data) and the secondary use of data (for registries that rely on data linkage from multiple sources) by defining:

- The main categories of data to be recorded in EHRs;
- The European Electronic Health Record Exchange Format;
- The EHR system requirements (i.e. the general requirements and the interoperability and security requirements);

- The categories of data that must be made available for secondary use;
- The purposes for which the secondary use of data is allowed;
- The requirements for dataset description and metadata;
- The requirements for data quality and utility.

The Regulation will also establish the necessary EU infrastructures and governance mechanisms.

3.5.1 EHDS Rules on the Primary Use of Data

According to Art.2.2 (d) of the EHDS Regulation, “primary use of electronic health data means the processing of electronic health data for the provision of healthcare to assess, maintain or restore the state of health of the natural person to whom that data relates, including the prescription, dispensation and provision of medicinal products and medical devices, as well as for relevant social, administrative or reimbursement services”.

Hence, in the case of disease registries/HIS, health data are collected mainly for primary purposes and eventually used for secondary purposes if a valid legal base exists.

3.5.2 Main categories of health data for EHR

The EHDS Regulation defines the main categories of health data that must be recorded/registered by health professionals in electronic format in the EHR system and that data subjects should have the right to access through “Electronic Health data Access Services” (i.e. online service such as a portal or a mobile application) at national, regional or healthcare provider levels.

Table 8: Electronic Health data categories (EHDS)

Electronic health data category	Main characteristics of electronic health data included under the category
Patient summary	<p>Electronic health data that includes important clinical facts related to an identified person and that is essential for the provision of safe and efficient healthcare to that person. The following information is part of a patient summary:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Personal details; 2. Contact information; 3. Information on insurance; 4. Allergies; 5. Medical alerts; 6. Vaccination/prophylaxis information, possibly in the form of a vaccination card; 7. Current, resolved, closed or inactive problems including in an international classification coding; 8. Textual information related to medical history; 9. Medical devices and implants; 10. Medical or care procedures; 11. Functional status; 12. Current and relevant past medicines; 13. Social history observations related to health; 14. Pregnancy history; 15. Patient provided data; 16. Observation results pertaining to the health condition; 17. Plan of care; 18. Information on a rare disease such as details about the impact or characteristics of the disease.
Electronic prescription	Electronic health data constituting a prescription for a medicinal product as defined in Article 3(k) of Directive 2011/24/EU.
Electronic dispensation	Information on the supply of a medicinal product to a natural person by a pharmacy based on an electronic prescription.
Medical image and image report	Electronic health data related to the use of or produced by technologies that are used to view the human body in order to prevent, diagnose, monitor, or treat medical conditions.
Laboratory result	Electronic health data representing results of studies performed notably through in vitro diagnostics such as clinical biochemistry, haematology, transfusion medicine, microbiology, immunology, and others, and including, where relevant, reports supporting the interpretation of the results.
Discharge report	Electronic health data related to a healthcare encounter or episode of care and including essential information about admission, treatment and discharge of a natural person.

3.5.3 European Electronic Health Record Exchange Format

These minimum electronic health data categories should be included in EHRs and shared both within and across countries through the European Electronic Health Record Exchange Format.

The European Exchange Format, to be defined by means of implementing acts of the EHDS Regulation, will have to be: commonly used; machine-readable; and allow transmission of personal electronic health data between different software applications, devices and healthcare providers. The format should support transmission of structured and unstructured health data and shall include the following elements (Article 6):

- Harmonised datasets containing electronic health data and defining structures, such as data fields and data groups for the representation of clinical content and other parts of the electronic health data;
- Coding systems and values to be used in datasets containing electronic health data;
- Technical interoperability specifications for the exchange of electronic health data, including its content representation, standards and profiles.

The EHDS Regulation also sets out the essential requirements for EHR systems in order to promote interoperability, security and data portability of such systems, which would also allow data subjects to control their electronic health data more effectively.

Until the EHDS Regulation is formally adopted, along with its implementing Acts, the 2019 Recommendation on European Electronic Health Record Exchange Format³⁶ could be used as best practices towards the interoperability of EHRs. The Recommendation proposes the following standards:

Health information domains	Content representation for cross-border exchange
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patient Summary • ePrescription/eDispensation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Health Level Seven (HL7) Clinical Document Architecture (CDA) Release 2 Level 3 and Level 1 (PDF (3)/A).
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Laboratory results • Medical imaging and reports • Hospital discharge reports 	<p><u>For laboratory results, medical imaging reports and hospital discharge reports:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Health Level Seven (HL7) Clinical Document Architecture (CDA) Release 2 Level 3 or Level 1 (PDF (1)/A). <p>For medical imaging:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine (DICOM).

The eHealth Network Guidelines on the electronic exchange of health data under Cross-Border Directive 2011/24/EU Patient Summary - Release 3.3 (June 2023)³⁷ further propose an effective use of standards to support the interoperability of clinical documentation, stressing that the use of “preferred code systems” for data elements in the dataset allows an unambiguous exchange of clinical information. Nevertheless, the final aim is to converge on the use of international coding systems, including emerging international standards.

Accordingly, the Guidelines propose the adoption of CEN/ISO 27269:2021 Health informatics - International Patient Summary standard, which would deliver a single, common International Patient Summary (IPS), comprising core content and compatible with both HL7 standards - CDA and FHIR.

3.5.4 Electronic Health Records (EHRs) System Requirements for Interoperability

Annex II of the EHDS Regulation sets out the EHR system requirements, which apply *mutatis mutandis* to products claiming interoperability with EHR systems. Hence, disease registries that communicate with EHR systems will need to comply with EHR systems requirements, as set forth by the EHDS Regulation.

According to the Regulation, an EHR system must consist of two core elements which form an integral part of the software:

- The interoperability component:
 - EHR systems must have the ability to interact with software applications and devices from the same or different manufacturers in order to transfer and receive personal electronic health data;
 - The technical specifications with regard to the health record exchange format will be determined by the European Commission with implementing acts. This exchange format will have:
 - To be commonly used;
 - To provide health data in a machine-readable format;
 - To support the transmission of structured and unstructured health data.
- The logging component:
 - EHR systems must be able to record logging information about access to personal electronic health data by users of the system. As a minimum standard, the logging information shall contain the following information on each time the data is accessed:
 - Identification of the health provider or other individuals having accessed personal electronic health data;
 - Identification of the specific individuals having accessed to personal electronic health data;
 - Categories of data accessed;
 - Time and date of access;
 - Origin(s) of data.

These two components of EHR systems are referred to as “harmonised components”.

In addition, EHR systems must comply with the essential requirements defined in Annex II of the proposal. For example, the requirements for interoperability are as follows:

- Where an EHR system is designed to store or intermediate personal electronic health data, it shall provide an interface enabling access to the personal electronic health data processed by it in the European health record exchange format, by means of the European interoperability component for EHR systems;
- Where an EHR system is designed to store or intermediate personal electronic health data, it shall be able to receive personal electronic health data in the European health record exchange format, by means of the European interoperability component for EHR systems;
- Where an EHR system is designed to provide access to personal electronic health data, it shall be able to receive personal electronic health data in the European health record

exchange format, by means of the European interoperability component for EHR systems;

- An EHR system that includes a functionality for entering structured personal electronic health data shall enable the entry of data with granularity sufficient to enable the provision of the entered personal electronic health data in the European health record exchange format;
- The harmonised components of an EHR system shall not include features that prohibit, restrict or place undue burden:
 - On authorised access, personal electronic health data sharing, or use of personal electronic health data for permitted purpose;
 - On authorised exporting of personal electronic health data for the reasons of replacing the EHR system by another product.

The Regulation also establishes a mandatory scheme of self-conformity assessment for EHR systems marketed in the EU, by which providers can prove compliance with the essential requirements on interoperability and security defined in Annex II of the Regulation.

All commercial EHR system operators must also meet a set of obligations regarding: technical documentation (Article 24); the EU declaration of conformity (Article 26); and CE marking. A market surveillance authority responsible for EHR systems will be established to monitor compliance. Moreover, the proposal establishes voluntary labelling of wellness applications, interoperable with EHR systems, and sets up an EU database in which certified EHR systems and labelled wellness applications will be registered (Article 30).

3.5.5 EHDS Rules on the Secondary Use of Health Data

According to Art 2.2 (e) of the EHDS Regulation, ‘secondary use of electronic health data’ means the processing of electronic health data for purposes set out in Chapter IV of this Regulation, other than the initial purposes for which they were collected or produced”.

Art. 33 of the EHDS Proposal defines the minimum categories of electronic data for secondary use. Accordingly, data holders have the obligation to make the following categories of electronic data available for the secondary use in accordance with the provisions of the Regulation:

- Electronic health data from EHRs;
- Data on factors impacting on health, including socio-economic, environmental and behavioural determinants of health;
- Aggregated data on healthcare needs, resources allocated to healthcare, the provision of and access to healthcare, healthcare expenditure and financing;
- Pathogen data, impacting on human health;
- Healthcare-related administrative data, including dispensation, claims and reimbursement data;
- Human genetic, epigenomic and genomic data;
- Other human molecular data such as proteomic transcriptomic, metabolomic, lipidomic and other -omic data;
- Automatically generated personal electronic health data, through medical devices;
- data from wellness applications;

- Data on professional status, specialisation and institution of health professionals involved in the treatment of a natural person;
- Population-based health data registries (public health registries);
- Data from medical registries and mortality registries;
- Data from clinical trials, clinical studies and clinical investigations subject to Regulation (EU) 536/2014, Regulation [SOHO], Regulation (EU) 2017/745 and Regulation (EU) 2017/746, respectively;
- Other health data from medical devices;
- Data from registries for medicinal products and medical devices;
- Data from research cohorts, questionnaires and surveys related to health, after the first publication of results;
- Health data from biobanks and associated databases.

Accordingly, data processed in disease registries, will need to be made available for secondary use once the Regulation will come into force.

Art. 34.1 of the Regulation specifies the legitimate purposes for which health data access bodies can grant access to electronic health data for secondary use to health data users, namely:

- Public interest in the area of public and occupational health, such as activities for protection against serious cross-border threats to health and public health surveillance or activities ensuring high levels of quality and safety of healthcare, including patient safety, and of medicinal products or medical devices;
- Policy making and regulatory activities to support public sector bodies or Union institutions, agencies and bodies, including regulatory authorities, in the health or care sector to carry out their tasks defined in their mandates;
- Statistics, such as national, multi-national and Union level official statistics defined in Regulation (EU) No 223/200928 related to health or care sectors;
- Education or teaching activities in health or care sectors at the level of vocational or higher education;
- Scientific research related to health or care sectors, contributing to public health or health technology assessment, or ensuring high levels of quality and safety of healthcare, of medicinal products or of medical devices, with the aim of benefiting the end-users, such as patients, health professionals and health administrators, including:
 - Development and innovation activities for products or services;
 - Training, testing and evaluating of algorithms, including in medical devices, in-vitro diagnostic medical devices, AI systems and digital health applications;
 - Improving delivery of care, treatment optimisation and providing healthcare, based on the electronic health data of other natural persons.

Additionally, the Regulation expands the possibilities for the secondary use of electronic health data in the context of new technologies, research and innovation, education and other fields not previously covered by the GDPR legitimate purposes for processing sensitive data.

The Proposal for the EHDS Regulation seems to strike a right balance between the privacy/data protection principles contained in the GDPR and health, including research, innovation and new technologies.

Although the current compromised text of the Regulation, adopted on 14 March 2024, may not yet be considered definitive, the Proposal, as currently realised, seems to address appropriately two major challenges of the digital age, namely:

- The need to exploit the ever-increasing availability and use of digital health data;
- The harmonisation of data availability, use and exchange across EU countries.

This reform could substantially boost the EU internal market and position the EU at the forefront of health research and innovation.

The EHDS Proposal sets forth also the governance mechanisms for health data sharing and re-use, in particular:

- MS will have to establish Digital Health Authorities;
- MS will have to establish National Contact Points that will facilitate operations for the cross-border EU infrastructures;
- MS will have to establish Health Data Access Bodies, which will vest supervisory and intermediary functions between data holders and data users;
- Access to secondary health data will occur pursuant to data permits handled by the Health Data Access Bodies.

According to the Proposal, health-data access bodies must ensure that electronic health data can be uploaded by data holders and can be accessed by the data user in a secure processing environment; which must be subject to regular audits.

To comply with data protection legislation, data users should be able to download only non-personal electronic health data from the secure processing environment; i.e. anonymised or pseudonymised data, when the key is kept by the health data access body.

The Commission will adopt implementing acts that provide for the technical, information security and interoperability requirements for the secure processing environments.

The Commission will also adopt implementing acts facilitating the handling of data access applications for HealthData@EU (the EU EHDS infrastructure for the exchange of data for secondary uses), including a common application form, a common data permit template, standard forms for common electronic health data access contractual arrangements, and common procedures for handling cross-border requests.

3.5.6 EHDS Dataset description and data quality and utility label

According to Article 55 (Dataset description and datasets catalogue), the health data access bodies, through a publicly available and standardised machine-readable datasets catalogue, will have to provide information, in the form of metadata, about the available datasets and their characteristics.

A description of each dataset will have to include information concerning the source, the scope, the main characteristics, the nature of electronic health data and the conditions for making electronic health data available. The Commission will adopt implementing acts that set out the minimum information elements that data holders have to provide for datasets and their characteristics. In addition, health data holders will have to check, at least every year, that their datasets description in the national datasets catalogue is accurate and up to date.

In addition, ex Article 56 (Data quality and utility label) datasets made available through health data access bodies may have an EU data quality and utility label applied by the health data holders (which is mandatory for datasets collected and processed with the support of EU or national public funding).

The data quality and utility label will have to cover the following elements, where applicable:

- For data documentation: metadata, support documentation, data dictionary, format and standards used, provenance, and when applicable, data model;
- For assessment of technical quality: completeness, uniqueness, accuracy, validity, timeliness and consistency of the data;
- For data quality management processes: level of maturity of the data quality management processes, including review and audit processes, biases examination;
- For assessment of coverage: time period, population coverage and, when applicable, representativeness of population sampled, and average timeframe in which a natural person appears in a dataset;
- For information on access and provision: time between the collection of the electronic health data and their addition to the dataset, time to provide electronic health data following an electronic health data access application approval;
- For information on data modifications: merging and adding data to an existing dataset, including links with other datasets;
- Where a data quality and utility label accompany the dataset pursuant to Article 56, the health data holder shall provide sufficient documentation to the health-data access body for that body to confirm the accuracy of the label.
- Hence, data controllers of disease registries/HIS should provide a metadata catalogue describing the datasets they hold and provide for a data quality and utility label, where required.

Table 7 summarises the main requirements of the EHDS Regulation relevant for disease registries/HIS.

Table 7: Summary Table of EHDS Requirements

EHDS Elements	Requirements
Main Categories of Health Data for EHRs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patient summary; • Electronic prescription; • Electronic dispensation; • Medical image and image report; • Laboratory result; • Discharge report.
European Electronic Health Record Exchange Format	<p>Should include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Harmonised datasets containing electronic health data and defining structures, such as data fields and data groups for the representation of clinical content and other parts of the electronic health data; • Coding systems and values to be used in datasets containing electronic health data; • Technical interoperability specifications for the exchange of electronic health data, including its content representation, standards and profiles.
Electronic Health Records (EHRs) System Requirements for Interoperability	<p>EHR systems must comply:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • With the common specifications that will be adopted by the Commission by means of implementing acts; • With the essential requirements defined in Annex II. <p>All commercial EHR system operators must also meet a set of obligations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-conformity assessment for EHR systems marketed in the EU; • Obligations regarding technical documentation (Article 24); and • The EU declaration of conformity (Article 26). <p>Certified EHR systems and labelled wellness applications will need to be registered in the EU database (Article 30).</p>
Secondary Use of Health Data	<p>Data held in disease registries will need to be made available for secondary use.</p>
Dataset description	<p>Data controllers of disease registries will have to provide their datasets description, including metadata:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information concerning the source, the scope, the main characteristics, nature of electronic health data.
Data quality and utility label	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A data quality and utility label can be applied by the health data holders for datasets made available through health data access bodies; • A data quality and utility label is mandatory for datasets collected and processed with the support of Union or national public funding; • The data quality and utility label will have to cover the elements indicated in article 56.

4. Discussion

In the European Union, Member States are expected to meet the requirements set by data protection legislation in data processing operations as a pre-requisite for the implementation of a sustainable information system.

In CHIEF, an expert group is investigating how to enable the routine collection of EU-harmonised indicators for diabetes and other NCDs.

The implementation of the EHDS Regulation will require that all data controllers and data holders: a) will ensure that health information is collected and recorded according to harmonised data formats and coding systems; b) will ensure that databases are compatible with the Electronic Health Record (EHR) system, with which it communicates; and c) will adopt of the European EHR Exchange Format.

In this paper, we have presented the results of a literature review paving the ground for the development of a novel tool to measure data protection, interoperability and governance assessment (DIGA). The instrument will be proposed by CHIEF to implement a comprehensive self-assessment, aimed at generating quality improvement in data management, as well as reliable information and knowledge for policy-making.

The results of the literature review allowed us to respond to the initial sets of research objectives.

Our study reviewed the state of implementation of data linkage across disease registries/health information systems that process health data relative to NCDs. Consequently, we have identified best practices for the derivation of indicators. The results showed that there are still inconsistencies across Europe in different areas of investigation, although there have been projects showing improvements in this direction, in fulfilment of the current regulations.

We also identified interoperability requirements and best practices in health databases, disease registries and health information systems. In this regards, the various laws and regulation passed during the last 5 years have prepared the way for the implementation of the EHDS. However, the timelines and uniformity in the adherence to this process appears still rather uncertain, and will be particularly challenging in the complex field of NCD indicators. In this regards, establishing a solid alliance between institutions and disease registries seems a viable solution to speed up the process, and test it in a meaningful way in the broad area of chronic diseases, where high level clinical and epidemiological expertise are particularly relevant.

Finally, the above materials allowed us to compile a core set of high level recommendations on legal compliance and best practices for data linkage and interoperability for policy makers and data holders of disease registries and information systems.

These can be summarised by the following summary points:

A. Recommendations on Data Linkage to estimate health indicators

In order to improve the potential for data linkage within the data protection frameworks, data controllers and processors should:

- Consider and assess the data linkage limitations applying to their contexts; which most often depend on several factors such as:
 - Research question and study design;
 - Original data quality and data lineage;
 - Data context knowledge;
 - Data linkage capacities and others.

- Continuously build data linkage capacities through:
 - Involvement of data domain experts;
 - Use of state-of-the-art technical linkage approaches and methodologies;
 - Implementing comprehensive data governance with a focus on all data quality dimensions;
 - Data transparency through comprehensive catalogues;
 - Data availability through various services and access technologies, etc.
 - Select the most appropriate technical methodologies for data linkage leveraging from multidisciplinary team of experts in social sciences, medical experts in the research domain, regulatory and decision-makers, as well as analytical and design experts.

B. Recommendations on Data Protection Requirements to comply with the GDPR

Data controllers and processors should:

- Ensure that a valid legal/lawful base for data processing in their registries/HIS/databases is in place and appropriately documented;
- Ensure that their registries/HIS/databases allow the exercise of data subject rights:
 - By establishing procedures to provide information and communications to data subjects;
 - By envisaging system functionalities (e.g. on-line requests on the system platform) that grant patients access to their data and allow updates, rectifications, erasures, portability, etc.

In the context of the EHDS Regulation the rights to access, rectification, data access service (for the minimum categories of data contained in EHRs), which should provide an immediate answer (e.g. data should be directly downloadable from the electronic health data access service/portal). Hence, disease registries/information systems linked to EHR systems should be built in a way that is compatible with the exercise of these expanded rights.

- Fulfil accountability requirement by envisaging appropriate technical and organisational measures that promote and safeguard data protection in their processing activities, including the effectiveness of the measures (i.e. measures must be reviewed and updated when necessary). These measures should include:
 - Keeping records of processing activities;
 - Appointing a DPO, when required;
 - Carrying out a data protection impact assessment, when required.
- Ensure appropriate security of personal data, including protection against unauthorised or unlawful processing and against accidental loss, destruction or damage, using appropriate technical or organisational measures (“integrity and confidentiality”) by:
 - Determining, prior to starting a processing activity, whether the purpose of processing can be achieved by using pseudonymised or anonymised data;
 - Assessing the severity and likelihood of the risks for data subjects in order to implement the security measures that are proportionate to the risks at a stake (e.g. through a DPIA);

- Implementing privacy-by-design (i.e. privacy enhancing human, organisational and technological measures are designed from the beginning and built in the registry/HIS, as well as routinely updated during the data processing life-cycle);
- Implementing privacy-by-default (i.e. establishing appropriate measures to ensure that only personal data which are necessary for the specific purposes are processed (e.g. software applications, computer programs or devices that have a default setting that minimise data collection and use);
- Using data protection engineering techniques, including Privacy Enhancing Technologies (PETS), e.g.:
 - Anonymisation (e.g. K-anonymisation, Differential privacy);
 - Pseudonymisation (e.g. Counter, Random number, Hash function, Hash-based message authentication code (HMAC), Encryption);
- Establishing appropriate procedures for data breach notification and communication, including procedures for the handling and management of data breaches such as Incident Response Plan, Business Continuity Plan, Disaster Recovery Plan, ISO standards.

By following these recommendations, data controllers of disease registries are able to comply with data protection and privacy requirements under the GDPR; which would also increase citizens trust and data availability.

C. Recommendations on Data Governance

Data controllers and data processors should ensure:

- Data Quality and Integrity:
 - Establish data quality standards and protocols for accurate and reliable data collection;
 - Regularly validate and verify data to ensure accuracy, completeness and timeliness;
 - Implement processes for data cleaning and de-duplication.
- Access Control and Transparency:
 - Control access to sensitive data through secure authentication and authorisation mechanisms;
 - Maintain audit trails to track access and modifications to data;
 - Ensure transparency in data handling practices and policies.
- Data Sharing and Collaboration:
 - Facilitate responsible data sharing with authorised parties for research and public health purposes;
 - Establish data sharing agreements that outline rights and responsibilities of all parties involved;
 - Protect against unauthorised data access or misuse during sharing.
- Governance Framework:
 - Develop and maintain a comprehensive data governance framework specific to disease registries;
 - Define roles and responsibilities for data stewards, data managers, and other stakeholders;

- Establish policies and procedures for data handling, retention, and disposal;
- Establish processes and standards for risk management and data protection engineering techniques.
- Training and Awareness:
 - Provide training on data governance principles and practices to staff involved in data management;
 - Raise awareness among registry participants about data protection and their rights regarding data access and use;
 - Stay informed about emerging data governance trends and best practices.
- Continuous Improvement and Compliance:
 - Regularly review and update data governance policies and procedures in response to changes in regulations or best practices;
 - Conduct internal audits and assessments to ensure compliance with data governance standards;
 - Incorporate feedback from stakeholders to improve data governance practices over time.

By following these recommendations, data controllers of disease registries can effectively manage data in a way that promotes trust, protects privacy, and supports meaningful research and public health initiatives.

D. Recommendations on the implementation of privacy-protective practices in data linkage

In order to implement privacy-protective best practices, data controllers and data processors should, according to the kind of data linkage to be carried out:

- use a unique personal identifiers for data linkages;
- use standard practices for creating pseudonyms from direct identifiers;
- use standard practices for deleting direct identifiers (such as names and patient numbers) for the performance of data linkages;
- use a standard process for the assessment of the risk of data re-identification;
- document the de-identification and/or pseudonymisation methodology and apply state of the art techniques;
- use standard practices for the treatment of attributes that pose a re-identification risk (such as rare diseases, exact dates, locations, or ethnic origins).

E. Recommendations on Interoperability in light of EHDS

- Data controllers/data holders of disease registries/HIS/health databases should ensure that health information is collected/recorded according to harmonised data formats and coding systems to allow within countries and cross-border optimal use of information and interoperability, as provided by European Recommendations and the EHDS Regulation;
- Data controllers/data holders of registries/HIS/health databases that communicate with an EHR system should ensure that the registry/HIS is compatible (fulfils the general, interoperability and security requirements envisaged for the EHR system) with the EHR system and use the European Electronic Health Record Exchange Format.

F. Recommendations on the secondary use of health data, databases and data quality in light of the EHDS

Data controllers/data holders should:

- ensure that data held in registries/HIS/health databases are made available for secondary use;
- provide a description of their datasets, including metadata (i.e. information concerning the source, the scope, the main characteristics, nature of electronic health data);
- obtain a data quality and utility label, when required.

Conclusions

In this literature review, we have provided an overview of the state of implementation of data linkage across disease registries and health information systems that process health data that are needed for the provision of accurate NCD indicators. We also identified interoperability requirements and best practices in health databases, as well as a synopsis of the main features required for adherence with the regulation of the EHDS.

These results will be used for the development of a novel tool to measure data protection, interoperability and governance assessment (DIGA) in disease registries and health information systems.

The materials allowed to compile a core set of high level recommendations on legal compliance and best practices for data linkage and interoperability for policy makers and data holders of disease registries and information systems.

The recommendations shall be applied to support the implementation of a sustainable information system, enabling the periodic collection of EU-harmonised NCD indicators.

Nomenclature

Resource Identification Initiative

Not applicable to submitted paper.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest. The authors also declare that they have no conflict of interest in relation to the production of the paper.

Author Contributions

All authors provided a substantial contribution to the production of the manuscript. CTDI conceived and drafted the paper, ER, IP and TB integrated and reviewed it.

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